

1. Most recent significant changes in the legal framework of Republic of Iraq

Adoption of a new electoral law in the republic of Iraq happen in early November 2020, is a complete departure from those passed since 2003. Instead of adopting one electoral district as in the 2005 elections – the first after the 2003 Iraq invasion – or designating each of Iraq’s 18 governorates as a single district like in the three subsequent elections, this new law divides Iraq into 83 electoral districts. These districts are based on the number of quota seats set aside for women in parliament, as the Constitution requires that 25% of the parliament’s 329 seats be designated for women. Which make clear that women should enjoy equal rights to men and that in the republic of Iraq cases the legal framework is significant changes by adding they should take temporary special measures to achieve de facto equality for women.^[1] After the establishment of the post-occupation political regime, the Iraqi parliament appeared inaccessible to independent candidates and small political parties. The electoral laws and systems that governed past elections allowed large and medium-sized parties and coalitions to win at the expense of independent candidates and others outside the circles of established political elites. The new electoral law tries to respond to a more open system by increasing electoral districts and adopting individual nomination procedures for candidates. Is clearly answering the observance of the principle of universal suffrage means that every citizen, upon coming up to the age fixed by the Constitution, laws, has the right to elect and to be elected to the bodies of state power, to local self-governments, other bodies of people’s (national) representation, to elective posts on the conditions and in line with procedures stipulated by the Constitution and laws.^[2]

On the other hand of the gaps that the division of electoral districts approved by the parliament appears to have officially “formalized” the administrative sectarian borders established through continuing civil strife since 2005 across a mix of such governorates as Baghdad, Nineveh, Kirkuk, and Diyala. It has also brought together into single electoral districts members of different clans that were previously separated geographically. Such a distribution may be workable in a homogeneous and stable country that does not suffer from internal divisions and crises and regional and national polarization. In countries like Iraq, these electoral districts could cause further divisions by encouraging competition between different sectarian, ethnic, and national groups and even spark new tribal and regional tensions to emerge. The intervention of political powers in dividing the electoral districts is clear in areas where they are guaranteed influence among the population. For example, the delineation of districts in al-Anbar governorate combined regions 320km apart into one district in order to join members of the same clan and ultimately guarantee their votes will go to a

specific candidate or party. The same applies to Kirkuk, which is divided between Arabs, Kurds and Turkmen, and to Diyala and Baghdad, which are both divided along sectarian lines. ^[3]

The main stakeholders in the process of adoption of a new electoral law in the republic of Iraq were the president & the parliament for demonstration the president's draft had set the minimum age for candidacy at 25, which the parliament later raised to 28. Raising the age for candidacy appears in contradiction with the number of young people in Iraqi society, most of whom led demonstrations in 11 governorates in October 2019. Six hundred of them were killed, and 20,000 were injured because of the security forces' use of excessive force. The refusal of the dominant powers in parliament to lower the age for candidacy highlights still their unwillingness to allow for a younger generation of leaders to emerge. ^[4]

Civil society organizations are somehow active in the electoral process in the Republic of Iraq. For mentioning the Iraqi Bar Association created a list of at least 50 lawyers from all Iraqi provinces for the IHEC National Office for past election. Even they also negotiated with IHEC to receive five more monitoring badges, expanding their reach in the activity of election observers which in return show positively impact elections – both encouraging voters to turn out as they know that independent observers are keeping an eye on parties as well as contributing post-election to public discussions and media coverage based on their first-hand experience poll watching. ^[5]

From the international observers who observed the last election in the Republic of Iraq, the EU election observation mission (EU EOM) commented on the observation undertaken and published Preliminary Statement. Inside the statement, they recommended transparency and engagement with stakeholders from Independent High Electoral Commission, and improvement on the legal framework and electoral system regarding its Restrictions, gaps and imprecisions result in lack of legal certainty and effective protection including the unclear whether equality of the vote is ensured by the current constituency delimitation or not. Inside the statement, they recommended transparency and engagement with stakeholders from Independent High Electoral Commission. ^[6]

Universal and regional international documents applicable to elections in the Republic of Iraq include Universal Declaration of Human Rights at the United Nations General Assembly in 1948, Convention on the Political Rights of Women (1952), Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) (1979) & Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD).^[7]

According to CEDAW General Recommendation 23 (1997) state that while removal of de jure barriers is necessary, it is not sufficient. Failure to achieve full and equal participation of women can

be unintentional and the result of outmoded practices and procedures which inadvertently promote men. The countries must have developed effective temporary strategies in an attempt to achieve equality of participation, a wide range of measures has been implemented, including recruiting, financially assisting and training women candidates, amending electoral procedures, developing campaigns directed at equal participation, setting numerical goals and quotas and targeting women for appointment to public positions such as the judiciary or other professional groups that play an essential part in the everyday life of all societies.^[8] Based on this the Republic of Iraq took special measures including The Constitution requires the representation of at least 25 per cent of women in the parliament's a principle reiterated in the new Election Law. One seat in each of the 83 constituencies is reserved for women. The Independent High Electoral Commission regulation requires that if no woman gets elected in a constituency, the male candidate that has won a seat with the least votes must give up the seat in favour of the woman that obtained the most votes among the female candidates. Even if it is still silent and need improvement on the eventuality of no female candidates in a constituency or of female candidates not obtaining any of the votes cast.^[9]

In the Republic of Iraq, the right to vote is granted to Iraqi citizens that are at least 18 years in the election year inside or outside of the country, are on the voter register, in possession of an electronic voting card and specific identification documents. In addition, they must be 'fully competent' but must have full legal capacity. Such a restriction is contrary to provisions of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), especially in light of the Civil Code allowing for a broad deprivation of legal capacity. This is a clear legislation silent on the political rights of persons with disabilities. No significant efforts were undertaken to reduce hindrances to their participation on Election Day. There are no reliable official data available on persons with disabilities (PwD) in Iraq. Civil society organizations (CSOs) estimate their number to be between four and ten million. No provision compels the Independent Higher Electoral Commission to take special measures to ensure and facilitate the exercise of their rights.^[10]

When we view reasonable restrictions on the right to be elected in the Republic of Iraq we can find that the Iraqi citizens which doesn't in the possession of a high school diploma or/and with a conviction for certain crimes are restricted from being elected. Candidates also must not fall under the provisions of the Law on the Commission for Accountability and Justice. As a conclusion let us view the limitations on campaign expenditure in the Republic of Iraq which is regulated by the Political Parties Law no. 36/2015, which permits campaigning without unreasonable limitations. The amount a political party or independent candidate can spend on campaigning is not regulated, and therefore there are no campaign spending limits in place. There are several other lacunae in the

campaign finance legislation: there is no limit on the amount or in-kind contribution a donor can give to a political party or candidate; it remains unclear if donors may later participate in public tender/procurement processes.

2. Executive summary of the new law to regulate and introduce voting through internet in the next legislative elections of the Republic of Iraq

When considering the use of electronic voting which already the republic of Iraq introduced electronic voting cards and the next step of used counting technologies, the compatibility of these technologies the existing constitutional and legal framework needs to be considered very carefully. The use of these technologies is contradictory to existing provisions in the legal framework, and require additional provisions to be drafted to cover the ways in which technologies impact electoral processes.^[11] Therefore, the electoral legal framework regarding electronic Voting must include the following important parts. As starting E-voting should be treated as the functional equivalent to special or postal ballots and non-electronic alternatives should always be accessible. If there is a desire to limit electronic voting to a specified group, the Iraq Independent higher electoral commission should clearly prescribe the eligibility requirements. (Some jurisdictions only allow out-of-district voters, disabled voters and those who live a fixed distance away from the polls to vote over the Internet.) Access to electronic voting should be broad enough to ensure that implementation costs are not overly disproportionate to traditional voting. Parliament should grant the electoral authority flexibility in choosing the methods of authenticating voters as long as the methods are secure and reliable. Electoral officials should work with diplomatic officials to determine which countries are safe to allow remote voting in. and last but not least the period for e-voting should be conducted over at least a week and end no earlier than the close of advance polls but before voting day. The period should be fair to e-voters but also allow the electoral authority time to react to technical problems.

On the transparency side Party- or candidate-appointed scrutineers should be able to view all source programming code and inspect physical technology. A formalized process should be created for academics and international observers to get similar access to ensure the integrity of the e-voting system. Decisions on whether to publicly post source code or use open source technology should not be legislated but should be left up to electoral officials. Electoral officials should be required to provide public reports on the security and integrity of the e-voting system, as well as which external reviewers approve the system. Legislation or regulations should ensure that observers or developers immediately report errors to election authorities. Last but not least

on the transparency side procedures should be in place to have election officials inform key stakeholders, including political parties, of security incidents.

Finally, contingency planning for worst-case scenarios must be clearly set in advance. Inside it must include: - Clear procedures should be created, preferably in the Iraq Elections Act, for cancelling electronic voting, notifying voters and allowing recasting of votes if privacy, security or integrity has been unacceptably compromised. The Act should list conditions under which officials may temporarily expand the online voting period if service is interrupted for more than a determined time. Requirements in the Act and regulations should be in place on how to treat invalid votes and other irregularities. Regulations should detail how electronic votes are handled during a recount, although we recommend that the Act provide judges with increased discretion as to whether e-votes should be recounted in the case of a close election result clear disaster recovery plan covering all known risks of disruption should be produced before each election. Last but not least the government should ensure that a technical response team, including leading Internet service providers, other departments, and anti-virus and securities vendors, is formed to identify and respond to potential threats during an election.

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